

borer, and leafhopper and moderate resistance to sheath rot, brown spot, and gall midge biotype 1.

Purnendu has strong seed dormancy for about 3 mo. Grain is golden with purple

apiculi. Mean grain dimensions are 7.9 × 2.8 mm with a test weight of 18.9 g. Kernels are white with a length-breadth ratio of 2.5. Hulling percentage is 79.5 and milling percentage is 73.5. Both alkali value (5.6)

and amylose content (26.1) are high.

A large amount of seed has been distributed through the minikit program to make the variety available to farmers. ■

Jitendra, a new deepwater rice variety for Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal, India

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The Varietal Identification Committee of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research approved the release in 1994 of Jitendra (SF432) for deepwater areas in Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal, India. Jitendra is a pureline selection from land races. It was developed at RRS, Chinsurah. The variety is suitable for water depths of 100 cm or more.

The mean yield of the variety in national trials was 2.8 t/ha with a yield potential of 5.0 t/ha. It yielded 46% more than Tilakkachari and 33% more than Jalmagna. It ranked third in the 1992 advanced variety trial-deepwater (AVT-DW), fifth in the 1991 AVT-DW, and seventh in the 1990 AVT-DW over the pooled means. At Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh, Jitendra yielded 5 t/ha in 1989 with a maximum water level of 191 cm, and 4 t/ha in 1992 when the maximum water depth was 141 cm (see table).

Jitendra is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and flowers around the third week of October. It has tolerance for submergence, mainly through elongation and very good kneeing ability. Panicles are well exerted with long slender golden grains and purple apiculi. Grain dimension is 10.9 × 2.9 mm, with a test weight of 31.2 g. Kernels are white with a length-breadth ratio of 3.3. Hulling percentage is 79.7 and milling percentage is 72.5. The rice has intermediate alkali value (2.6) and amylose content (25.0). Seed dormancy is about 3 mo.

Jitendra has resistance to neck blast, brown planthopper, and whitebacked planthopper and moderate resistance to leafhopper and gall midge biotype 1. ■

Performance of Jitendra in national trials. India. 1988-92.

Year	Trial/site	Yield (t/ha)		Maximum water depth (cm)
		Jitendra	National check	
1988	<i>PVT-5</i> ^a		<i>Tilakkachari</i>	
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.2 ^a	nil	85
	Pusa, Bihar	1.0*	nil	140
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	1.2	1.1	70
	Canning, West Bengal	3.1	3.6	90
1989	<i>UVT-6</i> ^b		<i>Jalmagna</i>	
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	2.4	0.6	65
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	5.0	4.6	191
1990	<i>AVT-DM</i>			
	Pusa, Bihar	1.7	1.6	95
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.5	1.3	50
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	3.0*	2.1	200
1991	<i>AVT-DW</i>			
	Pusa, Bihar	2.4	2.2	na ^e
1992	<i>AVT-DW</i>			
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	4.0*	2.8	141
	Motto, Orissa	2.4	1.7	125

^aPVT-5 = Preliminary variety trial-5. ^bUVT-6 = Uniform variety trial-6. ^cAVT-DW = Advanced variety trial - deepwater. ^d* = significantly superior over national checks at the 5% level. ^ena = not available.

Seed technology

A simple method for producing F₁ hybrid seed for observational yield trials

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After good hybrid combinations are identified in test-cross nurseries, the next

step is to evaluate their performance in observational yield trials (OYT) before promoting the promising ones to regional or national trials.

With the numerous hybrids that need to be evaluated in OYT, it is often difficult to get proper space isolation to produce pure F₁ seed at a research farm. However, producing hand-crossed F₁ seed of many hybrids is laborious and often impractical. To overcome these problems, a simple method for producing a small quantity of relatively pure F₁ seed for conducting OYT was developed.

1. Layout for production of F₁ seed for observational yield trial.

All of the restorer lines of the hybrids to be produced are sown on the same day. Seedlings for each are transplanted 25-30 d after sowing within a 1-m² area, and spaced at 15 × 15 cm in alternate rows, leaving a 20-cm space all around the edge. The A lines of the hybrids to be produced are sown

2. Position of A (●) and R (x) lines in an isolated chamber.

on five or six different dates at a 6- to 7-d interval starting 2 wk before the seeding of the R lines. The aim is to achieve proper synchronization for the different A and R lines.

At the boot leaf stage of R lines, 2-m-high barriers are erected on three sides of the 1-m² plots, leaving a gap of 20 cm from the ground (Fig. 1). The open side is partially covered by the bamer from the adjacent plot. This space can be conveniently used for cultural operations, including supplementary pollination. Just before panicle emergence of the R lines, plants of the desired A line, which are at the same growth stage as the R lines, are moved and planted in the vacant alternate rows. To ensure higher outcrossing, supplementary

pollination using a stick should be carried out at anthesis 3-4 times/d for a week.

Within each 1-m² plot, there are 15 plants of the R line in 3 rows and 10 plants of the A line in 2 rows (Fig. 2). With a very conservative estimate of only 5 tillers/plant of the A line, 80 spikelets/panicle, and only a 40% outcrossing rate, about 1,600 seeds weighing 30-35 g can be easily obtained.

For conducting an OYT, 20-25 g of seed are more than adequate. The method proposed can be used to produce many hybrids for OYT. The advantages are

- comparatively pure seed of numerous F₁ hybrids can be produced in a limited area,
- the problem of obtaining proper synchronization of parental lines in hybrid seed production can be easily overcome, and
- F₁ seed for conducting OYT can be produced with the very limited quantity of R line seed available initially. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Proline content in rice seedlings grown under saline conditions

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Severe salinity stress induces numerous metabolic irregularities in plants. Researchers have assumed that a large (up to 100 times the normal) accumulation of free-

proline is one of the most dramatic characteristics of the stress.

We surface-sterilized 20 seeds for each of four rice varieties: salt-tolerant Pokkali and IR42 and salt-sensitive MI 48 and Perla. After sterilization, these varieties were grown in plastic pots filled with gravel and Hoagland nutrient solution enriched with 0.7% NaCl solution. Other seeds were sown under the same conditions without salts. A pH value of 5.0 was maintained for both. Plants were placed in growth cham-

bers with 30/25 °C day/night temperature, 14 h of light, and 70% relative humidity. The experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications across three seasons. All measurements were taken 7 and 21 d after transplanting.

Plant material (0.5 g) was homogenized in 10 ml of 3% aqueous sulfosalicylic acid solution and filtered. Two ml of filtrate were reacted in 2 ml acid-ninhydrin and 2 ml of glacial acetic acid for 1 h at 100 °C. The reaction was terminated in an ice bath. To the reaction mixture, 4 ml of toluene were added and mixed vigorously with a test tube stirrer for 15-20 s. The chromophore containing toluene was aspirated from the aqueous phase, warmed to room temperature, and the absorbance read at 520 nm using toluene for a blank.

The proline concentration was determined from a standard curve and calculated on a fresh weight basis as

$$\text{mmol proline/g fresh weight material} = \frac{[(\text{mg proline/ml} \times \text{ml toluene}) / 115.5 \text{ mg/mmol}] / [\text{g sample} / 5]}{1}$$

The proline content for all varieties exposed to salt stress significantly increased (see table). The highest proline concentrations were observed in salt-sensitive varieties

Proline concentration in rice seedlings cultivated under normal and stress conditions.^a

Variety	Proline concentration (mg/g fresh matter)					
	7d			21 d		
	Control	Stress	% over control	Control	Stress	% over control
Pokkali	52.11 c	98.87 d	189	66.10 c	117.60 d	177
IR42	58.98 b	106.00 c	179	68.70 b	163.27 b	237
MI 48	45.03 d	156.68 a	347	59.46 d	180.11 a	302
Perla	68.19 a	153.28 b	224	71.10 a	194.44 c	273
SE	+0.92	+0.54		+0.42	+0.88	
CV(%)	2.84	0.72		1.45	0.93	

^a Values followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level according to DMRT.